

Chemistry and Cyclisation Reactions of Pyrimidothienoquinoxaline Derivatives. Part-IV^Y

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The pyrimidothienoquinoxaline (2a; R = OH), derived from 1 and formamide, is thionated and chlorinated to 2b (R = SH) and 2f (R = Cl) respectively. Treatment of 2f with hydrazine produces 2j (R = NHNH₂), the latter giving 3a (R = SH) with carbon disulphide, 3c (R = CH₂CO₂Et) with diethyl malonate, and 4 with nitrous acid. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of some of the products have been assessed.

In continuation of our previous work on synthesis of quinoxaline derivatives¹, the present study deals with synthesis of a new series of pyrimidothienoquinoxaline systems of promising biological properties.

Treatment of ethyl 3-aminothieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline-2-carboxylate (1)² with formamide gives pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxalin-4(3*H*)-one (2a) (Scheme 1).

Thionation of 2a by phosphorus pentasulphide in dry pyridine gives pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline-4(3*H*)-thione (2b) which on alkylation with methyl iodide, ethyl iodide and benzyl chloride produces the corresponding 4-alkylthiopyrimido derivatives 2c-e respectively. The ir spectrum of 2b shows bands at 3 450 (NH), 1 570 (C=N) and 1 230 cm⁻¹ (C=S). Such thione form is further confirmed by its electronic spectrum showing large red-shift at λ_{\max} 470 nm due *n*- π transition when compared to that of 4-alkylthio compounds (2c-e) at λ_{\max} 410 (Table 1). Compound 2a is chlorinated with a mixture of phosphorus oxychloride and phosphorus pentachloride to 4-chloropyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (2f) which on treatment with aniline, dimethylamine and diethylamine gives 2g, h and i respectively. Treatment of 2f with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol gives 4-hydrazinopyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (2j) which

TABLE 1—UV SPECTRAL MEASUREMENTS^a FOR THE COMPOUNDS 2b-e

Comp no.	Band 1 λ_{\max} (nm)/ (10 ³ ϵ_{\max})	Band 2 λ_{\max} (nm)/ (10 ³ ϵ_{\max})	Band 3 λ_{\max} (nm)/ (10 ³ ϵ_{\max})	Band 4 λ_{\max} (nm)/ (10 ³ ϵ_{\max})	Band 5 λ_{\max} (nm)/ (10 ³ ϵ_{\max})
2b	470 (4.00)	435 (6.40)	390 (9.20)	340 (6.40)	260 (2.16)
c	410 (0.28)	350 (1.90)	280 (3.36)	—	—
d	410 (0.32)	350 (2.20)	290 (3.40)	255 (2.90)	—
e	410 (0.24)	350 (1.92)	290 (3.00)	250 (2.56)	—

^a In CDCl₃ (5 × 10⁻⁵ M).

is similarly prepared by treatment of the alkylthio compounds 2c-e with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol. The ir spectrum of 2j shows bands at 3 320–3 200 (NH, NH₂) and 1 650 cm⁻¹ (C=N). Its mass spectrum shows molecular ion peak at *m/z* 268 which is in agreement with its molecular formula C₁₂H₈N₆S. The hydrazino compound (2j) condenses with benzaldehyde and its *p*-methoxy- and *p*-dimethylamino substituents in acetic acid or ethanol/piperidine to give the corresponding 4-arylidenehydrazinopyrimido[4',5':4,4]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxalines (2k-m) respectively. Their ir spectra show (NH) bands at 3 200–3 180 (NH) and 1 590–1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N). Treatment of 2j with acetic anhydride gives α,β -triacetyl-4-hydrazinopyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (2n). Its ir spectrum shows absence of NH band and presence of C=O band at 1 740–1 710 cm⁻¹. Its ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) shows signals at δ 2.6 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.7 (6H, s, 2 × CH₃), 9.1 (1H, s, CH) and 7.8–8.6 (4H, m, ArH). Refluxing 2j with ethyl chloroformate in pyridine gives β -*N*-ethoxycarbonyl-4-hydrazinopyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (2o). Its ir spectrum shows bands at 3 480–3 320 (NH) and 1 720 cm⁻¹ (C=O ester). Its ¹H nmr spectrum (DMSO) shows signals at δ 1.2–1.4 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.2–4.6 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.8–8.8 (5H, m, NH + ArH), 9.3 (1H, s, CH) and 13 (1H, s, NH). Refluxing 2j with phthalic anhydride in glacial acetic acid or by fusion gives 2-(pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxalin-4-yl)phthal-

azin-1,4(3*H*)-dione (2q). Its ir spectrum shows bands at 3 200 (NH), 1 800, 1 750 (C=O 1,4-dione). Its ¹H nmr spectrum (DMSO) shows signals at δ 3.7 (1H, s, NH), 7.9–8.2 (8H, m, ArH) and 8.7 (1H, s, CH pyrimidine ring). Treatment of 2j with acetylacetone in ethanol gives 4-(3,5-dimethylpyrazol-1-yl)pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (2p). Its ir spectrum shows the absence NH band. Its ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) shows signals at δ 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.0 (1H, s, CH pyrazole ring), 7.7–8.5 (4H, m, ArH) and 9.1 (1H, s, CH pyrimidine ring). Refluxing 2j with carbon disulphide gives 3-mercapto-*s*-triazolo[4'',3'' : 1',6']pyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]-thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (3a) which is alkylated with ethyl iodide to the corresponding 3-ethylthio derivative (3b). Similarly 2j undergoes ring closure reactions on treatment with diethyl malonate and/or nitrous acid to ethyl-*s*-triazolo[4'',3'' : 1',6']pyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline-3-methylcarboxylate (3c) and tetrazolo[4'',3'' : 1',6']pyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (4) respectively. Their ir spectra show disappearance of NH and NH₂ bands. The ¹H nmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of 3c shows signals at δ 1.2–1.4 (3H, t, CH₃), 4.1–4.4 (4H, q, 2×CH₂), 9.5 (1H, s, CH pyrimidine ring) and 7.8–8.5 (4H, m, ArH). Its ir spectrum shows band at 1 730 cm⁻¹ (C=O).

Biological activity³ : As revealed from results of agar diffusion tests, most of the compounds showed significant bactericidal with considerable antifungal activities against some strains (Table 2).

TABLE 2—ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTIFUNGI DATA (INHIBITION ZONE IN mm) AGAINST ORGANISMS^a

Compd no	<i>Bc</i>	<i>St</i>	<i>Ec</i>	<i>Ksp</i>	<i>Pn</i>	<i>Afl</i>	<i>Afu</i>	<i>Fs</i>
2a	—	—	7	10	—	—	—	—
b	—	—	7	9	—	—	—	—
f	—	7	6	9	10	8	8	6
i	8	7	7	9	7	—	—	—
j	6	—	6	12	7	8	6	10
m	—	—	7	10	—	—	—	—
3a	6	—	7	10	—	—	—	—

^a *Bc* = *Bacillus cereus*, *St* = *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Ec* = *Escherichia coli*, *Ksp* = *Klebsiella sp.*, *Pn* = *Penicillium nigricans*, *Afl* = *Aspergillus flavus*, *Afu* = *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Fs* = *Fusarium solani*.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP3-100 spectrophotometer, electronic spectra on a Shimadzu 200 spectrophotometer, nmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer (90 MHz) and mass spectra (solid samples) on a MS-902, AET instrument. All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N and S analyses.

Pyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline-4(3*H*)-one (2a) : A mixture of ethyl 3-aminothieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline-

2-carboxylate (1; 2.7 g, 0.01 mol) in formamide (30 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solid that separated on cooling was crystallised from ethanol, (2 g, 75%), m.p. > 360°; ν_{\max} 3 080 (NH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

Pyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline-4(3*H*)-thione (2b) : A mixture of 2a (2.5 g, 0.01 mol) and phosphorus pentasulphide (2 g, 0.01 mol) in dry pyridine was refluxed for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled, diluted with water and the separated solid was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals (2 g, 80%), m.p. 340°.

4-Alkylthiopyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxalines (2c-e) : A mixture of 2b (0.27 g, 0.001 mol) and the corresponding alkyl halide (0.002 mol), namely, methyl iodide, ethyl iodide and/or benzyl chloride, in ethanol (20 ml) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.001 mol) was refluxed for 30 min. The solid that separated in each case on addition of water was crystallised from acetic acid as yellow crystals : 2c, (75%), m.p. 249°; d, (68%), 210°; e, (75%), 210°; 2c δ (CDCl₃) 2.8 (3H, s, CH₃), 9.2 (1H, s, pyrimidine ring), 7.8–8.5 (4H, m, ArH); 2d δ 1.4–1.6 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.3–3.6 (2H, q, CH₂), 7.7–8.4 (4H, m, ArH), 9.1 (1H, s, pyrimidine ring).

4-Chloropyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (2f) : A mixture of 2a (2.5 g, 0.01 mol), phosphorus pentachloride (2.54 g) and phosphorus oxychloride (5 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The cooled mixture was then poured over ice and the solid that separated was crystallised from ethanol as brown crystals (2 g, 80%), m.p. 245–46° (Found : Cl, 12.34. C₁₂H₅N₄SCl calcd. for : Cl, 12.18%).

Reactions of 4-chloropyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (2f) with amines (2g-i) : A mixture of 2f (0.45 g, 0.002 mol) and amines, namely, aniline (0.002 mol), dimethylamine (3 ml) and/or diethylamine (3 ml) in absolute ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solid that separated in each case was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals : 2g, (0.35 g, 65%), m.p. 278–80°; ν_{\max} 3 240 (NH), 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); 2i (0.40 g, 75%), 165–66°, δ (CDCl₃) 1.3–1.5 (6H, t, (CH₃)₂), 3.7–3.9 (4H, q (CH₂)₂), 7.7–8.5 (4H, m, ArH), 8.7 (1H, s, pyrimidine ring).

4-Hydrazinopyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxaline (2j) : 2f or 2c-e (0.01 mol) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (5 ml) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) for 2 h. The solid that separated on cooling was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals (2.6 g, 80%), m.p. 284–85°.

4-Arylidenehydrazonopyrimido[4',5' : 4,5]thieno[2,3-*b*]quinoxalines (2k-m). **General procedure** : A mixture of 2j (0.54 g, 0.002 mol) and benzaldehyde, *p*-methoxybenzaldehyde and/or *p*-*N*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.002 mol) was refluxed in acetic acid or in ethanol/piperidine mixture for 2 h. The solid that separated on cooling was crystallised from ethanol to give 2k as lemon yellow crystals (75%), m.p. 350–51°, 2l as orange crystals (80%), m.p. 325–26° and 2m as brown crystals (70%), m.p. 309–10°.

α, β -Triacetyl-4-hydrazinopyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-b]quinoxaline (2n) : A mixture of 2j (0.54 g, 0.002 mol) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The cooled mixture was then poured in water and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as lemon yellow crystals (0.36 g, 70%), m.p. 220–21°.

β -N-Ethoxycarbonyl-4-hydrazinopyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-b]quinoxaline (2o) : A mixture of 2j (0.54 g, 0.002 mol) and ethyl chloroformate (3 ml) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The solid that separated on addition of water was crystallised from ethanol as brown crystals (0.39 g, 60%), m.p. 314–15°.

2-(Pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-b]quinoxalin-4-yl)phthalazin-1,4-(3H)-dione (2q) : A mixture of 2j (0.54 g, 0.002 mol) and phthalic anhydride (0.3 g, 0.002 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The cooled mixture was then poured in water and the resulting solid was crystallised from acetic acid as yellow crystals (0.33 g, 58%), m.p. 339–40°.

4-(3,5-Dimethylpyrazol-1-yl)pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-b]quinoxaline (2p) : A mixture of 2j (0.54 g, 0.002 mol) and acetylacetone (2 ml) in absolute ethanol (15 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The solid that separated was crystallised from ethanol-acetic acid mixture (1 : 1) as pale yellow crystals (0.3 g, 60%), m.p. 238–39°.

3-Mereapto-s-triazolo[4'',3''':1',6']pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-b]quinoxaline (3a) : A mixture of 2j (0.54 g, 0.002 mol) and CS₂ (10 ml) in dry pyridine (15 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. Water (10 ml) was then added to the cooled mixture and the resulting solid was crystallised from ace-

tic acid as red crystals (0.35 g, 65%), m.p. 320–21°; ν_{\max} 3700–3560 (NH), 1550 (C=N), 1220 cm⁻¹ (C=S).

3-Ethylthio-s-triazolo[4'',3''':1',6']pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-b]quinoxaline (3b) : To an ethanolic solution of 3a (0.62 g, 0.002 mol) and anhydrous sodium acetate was added ethyl iodide (10 ml) and the mixture stirred for 1 h. The solid that separated on addition of water (10 ml) was crystallised from ethanol as orange crystals (0.4 g, 65%), m.p. 158–59°; δ (CDCl₃) 1.5–1.7 (3H, t, CH₃), 3.4–3.7 (2H, q, CH₂), 9.1 (1H, s, CH), 7.8–8.6 (4H, m, ArH).

Ethyls-triazolo[4'',3''':1',6']pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-b]quinoxaline-3-methylcarboxylate (3c) : A mixture of 2j (2.68 g, 0.01 mol) and diethyl malonate was refluxed for 3 h. The solid that separated was crystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals (1.8 g, 70%), m.p. 244–45°.

Tetrazolo[4'',3''':1',6']pyrimido[4',5':4,5]thieno[2,3-b]quinoxaline (4) : To a mixture of 2j (2.68 g, 0.01 mol) and sodium nitrite solution (15 ml) was added dropwise 10% HCl at 0° while stirring for 30 min. The solid that separated was crystallised from ethanol as brown crystals (1.6 g, 60%), m.p. 289–90°.

References

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